

Sex Differences and Adjusted Efficacy in Nutraceutical Lipid Management

Matteo Acanfora¹, Luca Acanfora², Gaia Tamellini³ & Alberto Vassallo¹

¹*Institute of Endocrine and Metabolic Sciences, Istituto di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) Ospedale San Raffaele, Milan, ITA, Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele, Milan, ITA.*

²*Department of Internal Medicine, Civil Hospital of Ovada, Ovada, Alessandria, ITA.*

³*Department of Public Health and Forensic Medicine, University of Pavia, Pavia, ITA.*

Corresponding author: Matteo Acanfora (acanfora.matteo@hsr.it)

ABSTRACT

Background. Nutraceuticals are commonly used in lipid-lowering therapy, particularly for patients with polygenic hypercholesterolemia and low-to-moderate cardiovascular (CV) risk. However, their efficacy is often derived from pre–post observational studies lacking placebo controls, making results prone to overestimation due to regression to the mean and behavioral factors.

Objective. To introduce placebo-relative correction as a methodological tool to recalibrate efficacy estimates in nutraceutical studies without placebo arms, using a real-world cohort as a case example.

Methods. We applied placebo-relative correction to an 8-week observational study involving 20 patients treated with a nutraceutical combination (monacolin K 2.2 mg, berberine 500 mg, silymarin 80 mg). Active fractions (85.7% for nutraceuticals, 97.1% for statins) were derived from recent meta-analyses. LDL-C changes were recalculated accordingly. Sensitivity analyses (80–90% active fraction) and sex-based response analyses via logistic regression were conducted.

Results. Unadjusted LDL-C reduction was –17.47%. After correction, the estimated effect was –14.97% for nutraceuticals and –16.96% for statins. Men showed greater LDL-C reduction than women (–21% vs –16%). Female sex was an independent negative predictor of response (OR = 0.04, $p = 0.039$).

Conclusions. Placebo-relative correction is a feasible and conservative approach to enhance the interpretability of observational nutraceutical studies. While it cannot replace placebo-controlled trials, it adds methodological rigor by adjusting for non-specific effects. The observed sex-based differences also highlight the need for stratified analyses in future research.

Keywords: lipids; cardiovascular prevention; LDL-C; nutraceuticals; sex differences; placebo effect; bias; outcomes; efficacy; safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nutraceuticals—bioactive compounds derived from food sources—are increasingly incorporated into lipid-lowering strategies, particularly among patients who are reluctant to initiate statin therapy or who lack an indication. Agents such as red yeast rice (RYR, containing monacolin K, or MonK) and berberine (BBR) have demonstrated lipid-lowering potential and are widely used in clinical practice [1–3].

Despite their popularity, skepticism remains about their safety and effectiveness. It is well known that this is because regulators classify these compounds as foods without the controls necessary for medicinal approval. Until the regulatory gap is addressed, the scientific community has a responsibility to take action.

When it comes to effectiveness, it is less emphasized as methodological limitations of the supporting evidence often come from pre–post observational studies that lack control groups [4,5]. Without a placebo comparison, it is difficult to directly attribute changes in lipid levels to the intervention, which introduces a significant risk of bias [4].

In pharmacological research, placebo-controlled randomized controlled trials (RCTs) remain the gold standard for determining net treatment effects by isolating the specific contribution of the active compound from non-specific or behavioral effects. In contrast, the absence of control groups in many nutraceutical studies makes comparisons with pharmacologic therapies inherently asymmetrical. This discrepancy may lead to inflated efficacy claims and limit the integration of nutraceuticals into evidence-based clinical guidelines.

We demonstrate the feasibility and practical implications of this method using a real-world case study previously published on a nutraceutical combination.

Our goal is to promote placebo-relative correction as a conservative, standardized adjustment for improving the validity and credibility of observational nutraceutical research conducted without placebo arms.

2. METHODS

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Placebo-relative correction is an original method we developed to adjust the raw nutraceutical effects in observational studies by accounting for the contribution of placebo-related components. The approach involves multiplying the observed percentage change by an empirically derived *active fraction*—the proportion of the total effect attributable to the active compound(s). This correction estimates what the net treatment effect would likely have been if a placebo control group had been included.

In this study, active fraction values were drawn from recent large-scale placebo-controlled randomized trials and meta-analyses. The formula used is: *Corrected Effect (%) = Observed Effect (%) × Active Fraction*.

The conceptual foundation of this method is consistent with established pharmacological and statistical strategies designed to isolate treatment-specific effects. For example, ANCOVA models adjust post-treatment outcomes based on baseline values in pre–post analyses [6], and observational designs may incorporate placebo-analogue samples to identify and correct for bias [7]. These precedents support the theoretical plausibility and methodological soundness of our approach.

The active fractions applied in this study were as follows:

- Nutraceuticals: 85.7% [8].
- Low-intensity statins: 97.1% [9,10].

These values reflect the proportion of the total observed effect attributable to the pharmacological action of the compounds, excluding the placebo component.

2.2 Clinical Dataset Used for Application

As a case example, we used data from a prospective observational study we conducted in 2022 at a lipidology clinic of IRCCS Ospedale San Martino in Genoa, Italy. The study involved 23 adult patients with polygenic hypercholesterolemia and low-to-moderate cardiovascular (CV) risk, calculated using the Systemic Coronary Risk Estimation (SCORE) tool, which predicts the probability of death from CV disease within ten years (as <5% for

low to moderate CV risk). At that time, the LDL-C target in this population was under 116 mg/dL following the 2019 European Society of Cardiology (ESC)/European Atherosclerosis Society (EAS) guidelines for dyslipidemia management [11].

Patients failed to reach the LDL-C goal after at least three months of lifestyle changes; thus, they received a lipid-lowering nutraceutical as clinically indicated. The combination of the study (Normolip 5 Forte®, ESI), prescribed once daily at bedtime for 8 weeks, contained three main active ingredients: monacolin, with Mon K 2.2 mg (from RYR by *Monascus purpureus*), BBR hydrochloride 500 mg (from *Berberis aristata*), and silymarin 80 mg (from *Silybum marianum*). Other key features to participate in the study were:

- Baseline LDL-C between 130-189 mg/dL.
- Exclusion of major secondary causes/comorbidities (diet, medications, obesity, diabetes, hypothyroidism, any impairment of renal and hepatic functions, myopathies, other severe comorbidities), pregnancy, lactation, and known adverse events to any ingredients.
- No use of lipid-lowering drugs in the past two months, ensuring a clean baseline.
- No specific dietary restrictions outside of routine lifestyle and nutritional counseling.

This population mirrors the real-world patients most often considered for nutraceutical therapy: relatively young, at limited absolute risk, but in need of LDL-C reduction to meet primary preventive goals.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the entire cohort

Item	N = 23 patients
Age (years)	50,5 ± 14,6
Sex n. F/M (%)	15/8 (65,2%/34,8%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	24,8 ± 2,7
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	133,3 ± 10,8
Arterial hypertension (n)	2 (8,7%)
TC (mg/dL)	254,4 ± 28,2
LDL-C (mg/dL)	166,4 ± 24,9
HDL-C (mg/dL)	63,1 ± 17,1
TG (mg/dL)	128,6 ± 61,3
Smokers (n)	3 (13,0%)
SCORE (%)	2,4 ± 0,01

Data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for continuous variables, and as absolute number (percentage) for categorical variables. The table reports demographic, anthropometric, hemodynamic, and biochemical characteristics of the 23 enrolled patients before treatment. Abbreviations: BMI = Body Mass Index; TC = Total Cholesterol; LDL-C = Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol; HDL-C = High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol; TG = Triglycerides; SCORE = Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation (cardiovascular risk estimate, expressed as % over 10 years).

The primary outcome was the percentage change in low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) levels from baseline to 8 weeks, measured after at least 12 hours of fasting. Secondary outcomes included:

- Percentage changes in total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and triglycerides (TG);
- Reported adverse effects (RAEs);
- Changes in safety parameters: aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), creatine kinase (CK), and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR, CKD-EPI formula);
- Changes in lifestyle factors (diet, physical activity, smoking) and anthropometric measures (body mass index [BMI], systolic blood pressure [SBP], and waist circumference).

Data analyzed in 2022 were evaluated using MedCalc Statistical Software version 18.2.1 (MedCalc Software bvba, Ostend, Belgium, 2018). Normality tests (Shapiro-Wilk test) determined the appropriate statistical tests, with paired t-test samples (for normally distributed continuous variables) or Wilcoxon signed-rank test (when distributions were not normal).

2.3 Statistical Analysis

Raw LDL-C percentage reductions were recalculated for each patient. The mean and standard deviation were determined across the cohort.

Bootstrap resampling (10.000 iterations) estimated 95% confidence intervals (CIs), avoiding assumptions of normality.

The placebo-relative correction was applied using both 85.7% and 97.1% active fractions. A logistic regression model was used to identify predictors of achieving the minimum percentage LDL-C reduction, including covariates as sex, age, BMI, and LDL-C baseline levels.

Sensitivity analysis tested various active fractions (80%–90%) to assess robustness.

All data processing and visualizations of the present work were conducted in 2025 using Python 3.11 (alongside NumPy, pandas, statsmodels, and Matplotlib).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Original study Outcomes

Out of 23 patients initially enrolled, 3 were excluded (2 lost to follow-up, 1 discontinued due to myalgia without CK elevation). The final group consisted of 20 patients.

The “raw” mean LDL-C reduction after 8 weeks was: -17.47% (SD $\pm 6.88\%$) ($p < 0.05$).

No significant changes were observed in TC, HDL-C, or TG. There were no safety concerns, RAE, or lifestyle and anthropometric changes in the analyzed cohort.

3.2 Placebo-Relative Correction

After applying the placebo-relative correction for nutraceutical and statin scenarios, we obtained the mean LDL changes shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean LDL-C changes, before and after placebo correction using different active fraction scenarios.

Scenario	Mean LDL-C Change (%)
Raw (Observed)	-17.47%
Nutraceutical (85.7%)	-14.97%
Statin (97.1%)	-16.96%

Mean percentage change in low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) levels from baseline to 8 weeks, based on three scenarios: unadjusted (raw observed value), placebo-corrected using an active fraction of 85.7% (based on nutraceutical meta-analyses), and placebo-corrected using a 97.1% active fraction (based on low-intensity statin trials). The correction was applied using the formula: Corrected Effect (%) = Observed Effect (%) \times Active Fraction.

We also observed variability in the response to the compound in LDL changes (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Individual LDL-C (%) reduction after 8 weeks of nutraceutical treatment, with placebo corrections

Red dashed line: raw mean reduction (-17.47%). Green dashed line: placebo-relative corrected value (-14.97%, assuming 85.7% active fraction, nutraceuticals). Purple dashed line: placebo-relative corrected value (-16.96%, assuming 97.1% active fraction, statins). This figure illustrates patient-level variability in LDL-C response and demonstrates how placebo-relative correction recalibrates inflated raw estimates to more pharmacologically plausible values. The method aligns observational data with randomized-controlled expectations. Patients = 20.

3.3 Sensitivity Analysis

Active fractions ranging from 80% to 90% yielded corrected LDL-C reductions between -13.98% and -15.72%, respectively. These findings demonstrate that the placebo-relative correction remains within a clinically consistent and robust range, even when accounting for plausible variations in the assumed placebo effect.

3.4 Sex-Based Differences in Response

A logistic regression model identified female sex as a statistically significant negative predictor of LDL-C response, with reduced odds of achieving at least a –14.97% reduction (rounded to –15%)—the lower LDL-C changes seen after placebo-correction (see Table 2).

Table 2. Logistic regression analysis of predictors of LDL-C response ($\geq -15\%$ reduction after placebo-relative correction).

Predictor	OR	95% CI	p-value
Female sex	0.04	0.002–0.72	0.039
Age	1.01	0.95–1.07	0.68
LDL-C (baseline)	0.99	0.97–1.01	0.44
BMI	1.02	0.91–1.13	0.55

Binary logistic regression was performed to identify predictors of achieving at least a –15% reduction in LDL-C following an 8-week nutraceutical intervention. The model included sex, age, baseline LDL-C, and BMI as independent variables. A statistically significant negative association was observed for female sex (OR = 0.04, 95% CI: 0.002–0.72, $p = 0.039$), indicating lower odds of achieving the target LDL-C reduction in women. Other covariates were not significant predictors. Abbreviations: OR = Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; LDL-C = Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol; BMI = Body Mass Index. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$.

On average, men achieved a 21% reduction in LDL-C levels, while women showed a comparatively lower reduction of 16%.

4. DISCUSSION

This paper advocates for the systematic adoption of placebo-relative correction as a methodological tool in nutraceutical studies lacking a placebo control. Our case study illustrates how unadjusted observational pre–post data may substantially overestimate treatment efficacy due to non-specific effects. By applying a standardized correction factor derived from high-quality meta-analyses, researchers can improve the interpretability, comparability, and overall credibility of their findings in the absence of randomized controlled conditions.

4.1 Methodological Impact

As previously discussed, the main benefit of the placebo-relative correction—based on the concept of the active fraction—is its ability to estimate net treatment effects without a placebo group. This method helps to partially align nutraceutical research with pharmacological standards, where efficacy claims are usually compared against placebo-controlled outcomes [5].

This methodological improvement is especially important in lipidology, where LDL-C levels can vary due to behavioral, dietary, and temporal factors [12]. Even modest lifestyle changes or natural shifts toward the mean can create apparent improvements, possibly leading to an overestimation of treatment effectiveness in uncontrolled or non-randomized studies. The placebo-relative correction offers a practical way to address these confounding effects and improve the accuracy of observational data.

4.2 Interpretation of Findings

In our 20-patient observational cohort, the unadjusted mean LDL-C reduction was -17.47% . After applying the placebo-relative correction, the adjusted effect size was -14.97% , a value that more closely aligns with estimates from systematic reviews of placebo-controlled nutraceutical trials. This adjusted outcome is more conservative and arguably more credible than the raw reductions often reported in the literature [13].

A noteworthy finding was the emergence of a sex-based differential response. While such differences have been previously documented in statin studies, this is, to our knowledge, the first report suggesting that women may exhibit a less favorable response to nutraceutical interventions [14,15]. Potential explanations include sex-specific differences in pharmacokinetics, hormonal regulation, and fat distribution or metabolism. Although the small sample size limits the generalizability of this observation, the signal is sufficiently compelling to warrant further investigation.

We also observed considerable variability in individual treatment responses. While this may reflect multiple contributing factors—and the limited cohort size and short study duration preclude definitive conclusions—one likely explanation is the well-known issue of BBR bioavailability (with an average bioavailability of less than 1%) [2,16]. Even with the inclusion of silymarin, an enterocyte-level absorption enhancer (by inhibiting P-glycoprotein

[P-gp]—a membrane-bound efflux transporter located in the intestinal epithelium), interindividual variability remains high [2,3,16]. In our formulation, the silymarin dose (80 mg) was likely suboptimal compared to the ≥ 100 mg suggested in the literature, possibly diminishing its bioenhancing effect [3,16]. In this context, newer formulations utilizing phytosomal technology have shown promise in improving both the magnitude and consistency of BBR absorption and plasma concentrations. Indeed, phytosomal BBR has demonstrated providing up to 6- to 9-fold greater systemic exposure compared to standard BBR chloride. Such data suggest that a 500 mg dose of phytosomal BBR provides systemic exposure comparable to—and potentially greater than—1000–1500 mg of conventional formulations [16]. Moreover, recent studies have demonstrated that phytosomal formulations also significantly enhance the oral bioavailability of silymarin. For instance, phytosomal silybin (the main component of silymarin) exhibited 4.6–10 times greater bioavailability and superior hepatoprotective effects [17].

4.3 Limitations

This study has several limitations.

First, the dataset included only 20 patients, limiting statistical power and reducing the external validity of the findings.

Second, the proposed placebo-relative correction method relies on external estimates of the active fraction, primarily derived from meta-analyses. While these sources provide valuable aggregated data, they may not fully capture the specific characteristics of every study population or formulation, potentially introducing bias.

Third, the nutraceutical formulation used in this study contained relatively subtherapeutic doses compared to those commonly reported in the literature. Specifically, it included 2.2 mg of Mon K (compared to the standard 3 mg daily), 500 mg of BBR (vs. 1000–1500 mg daily), and likely an slight insufficient amount of silymarin (80 mg daily, versus ≥ 100 mg, which is considered necessary to enhance BBR bioavailability—when not using a phytosomic or liposomal formulation) [16]. These reduced dosages may also have contributed to a slightly inferior effect to those reported in previous studies [1–3].

However, despite the lower Mon K dose used in our study, one out of 23 patients (4%) experienced statin-like myalgia, without CK elevation, which resolved upon discontinuation

of the supplement. Although the sample size is small and the RAE was minor, this event is noteworthy. It aligns with EFSA's 2025 scientific opinion, which states that even 3 mg/day of Mon K may pose serious musculoskeletal and hepatic risks, and that no safe intake level can be established [18]. EFSA has also called for additional data to evaluate the safety of BBR-containing plant preparations due to concerns about gastrointestinal and other potential toxicities. However, formal risk assessments remain pending [19].

Finally, it is essential to emphasize that our proposed placebo-relative correction is not intended to replace a well-conducted, placebo-controlled randomized clinical trial. Instead, it serves as a compensatory methodological approach to improve the interpretability of unadjusted pre–post studies in the absence of a control group, and should not be viewed as a substitute for rigorous trial design.

4.4 Future Directions

Larger studies are needed to investigate sex-specific response patterns, confirm current findings, and explore their potential clinical implications.

We advocate for the inclusion of placebo-relative corrections in observational studies and real-world data analyses involving nutraceuticals. Making these corrections more accessible—through open-source calculators or integration into statistical software—would support methodological rigor in this field.

Critically, aligning nutraceutical research with pharmacological standards is essential to advance evidence-based clinical practice. To this end, regulatory frameworks should be updated to more closely reflect those governing medical products, particularly for nutraceuticals and supplements with pre-clinical demonstration of therapeutic potential and safety. Such agents are not intended for conventional food use or basic dietary supplementation in deficiency states. Rather, their diverse and clinically relevant applications call for appropriate regulations regarding commercialization, health claims, and targeted medical use.

Neglecting to establish such frameworks risks missing a key opportunity to broaden the therapeutic arsenal available to clinicians, especially in tailoring treatments to individual patient needs. This is particularly relevant given the demonstrated efficacy of certain compounds beyond lipidology. For instance, BBR and silymarin have proven potential

efficacy in managing hyperglycemia, and they are studied for pleiotropic effects, such as antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions, which are especially valuable in addressing chronic low-grade systemic inflammation, since it is viewed as a root cause of major chronic diseases and global mortality [20].

5. CONCLUSIONS

Our findings highlight the potential relevance of sex-specific responses in nutraceutical interventions, reinforcing the need for more personalized and stratified approaches in future research.

The proposed placebo-relative correction offers a pragmatic and scientifically grounded method to re-evaluate treatment efficacy in the absence of a control group. By applying this correction to real-world lipid-lowering data, we demonstrate its utility in mitigating the risk of overestimating clinical effects and bringing observational outcomes closer to those seen in RCTs.

If further validated, this approach could serve as a foundational methodological standard for nutraceutical efficacy assessments lacking placebo arms. Its adoption would contribute to more reliable data interpretation, facilitate cross-study comparisons, and ultimately promote more evidence-based integration of nutraceuticals into clinical practice.

6. STATEMENTS

All authors (MDs) have reviewed the final version and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Concept and design, acquisition, analysis, and interpretation of data: Matteo Acanfora, Luca Acanfora.

Drafting of the manuscript: Matteo Acanfora, Luca Acanfora, Alberto Vassallo, Gaia Tamellini.

Critical review of the manuscript for important intellectual content: Matteo Acanfora, Luca Acanfora, Gaia Tamellini, Alberto Vassallo.

Supervision: Alberto Vassallo, Gaia Tamellini.

Matteo Acanfora and Luca Acanfora equally contributed and shared first authorship. Alberto Vassallo and Gaia Tamellini equally contributed and shared second authorship.

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